

Article

The Effects of Predominantly Chemoautotrophic Versus Heterotrophic Biofloc Systems on Nitrifying Bacteria, Planktonic Microorganisms, and Growth of *Penaeus vannamei*, and *Oreochromis niloticus* in an Integrated Multitrophic Culture

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of predominantly chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic biofloc systems on ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB), and planktonic microorganisms in an integrated *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* integrated multitrophic culture. Shrimp and tilapia were stocked at a density of 400 shrimp m⁻² and 45 fish m⁻³, respectively. The trial consisted of two biofloc treatments, with three replicates each: chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic. The identification and quantification of the planktonic microorganisms (ciliates, flagellates, microalgae, and total bacteria) and nitrifying bacteria were carried out through direct counting and fluorescence in situ hybridization, respectively. At the end of the trial, heterotrophic treatment had resulted in higher total abundance of bacteria. The relative abundance of AOB and NOB in relation to the total abundance was less than 0.1% for both treatments. The system was dominated by flagellates in both treatment groups. The abundance of microalgae and ciliates was higher with chemoautotrophic treatment. After 43 days, the shrimp weights were higher in the chemoautotrophic group, while the final weights of the tilapia were not significantly different between the two treatments. The type of biofloc system (Chemoautotrophic vs. Heterotrophic) did not significantly alter the establishment of AOB and NOB in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* integrated multitrophic culture. The two treatments proved to be equally efficient for maintaining good water quality, but the chemoautotrophic treatment resulted in better shrimp growth. Thus, our study demonstrated that chemoautotrophic biofloc is a promising approach in integrated multitrophic aquaculture.

Keywords: IMTA; phytoplankton; zooplankton; chemoautotrophic bacteria

Key Contribution: We evaluated development of the nitrifying community in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* integrated culture with chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic biofloc systems. The results suggest that chemoautotrophic biofloc is a promising approach in integrated multitrophic aquaculture.

1. Introduction

Technologies in aquaculture with minimal or no water exchange are being developed with excellent growth results, as well as significant reduction of effluent discharge and wa-

ter use [1,2]. Among these technologies, the biofloc system (biofloc technology or BFT) has proven particularly successful. The most widespread BFT is based on the stimulation and growth of a diverse microbial community through amendment of the culture water with an organic carbon source. The maintenance of water quality is thereby ensured through microbial nutrient recycling and assimilation of organic and inorganic nitrogen [3,4]. This strategy promotes the growth of microbial aggregates composed of mainly heterotrophic but also chemoautotrophic (nitrifying) bacteria, microalgae, ciliates, flagellates, and protozoa, as well as exoskeletons, feces, and organic matter [5]. The use of this system can result in a reduction in water changes of more than 90%, without compromising water quality [6,7] and reduces land use through intensification of the culture [8,9].

In BFT systems, the main groups of bacteria that constitute the biofloc community are, in general, heterotrophic and chemoautotrophic bacteria, which control toxic nitrogenous compounds in the water [10]. Heterotrophic bacteria grow quickly in the presence of the provided organic carbon, nitrogen from feed and feces, and oxygen, decomposing and assimilating waste ammonia and organic matter in the process, transforming them into microbial biomass (microbial protein) [11]. Chemoautotrophic bacteria, which grow significantly slower than heterotrophs, play a key role in the nitrification process. Ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) act to convert ammonia into nitrite, which is subsequently used by nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB), forming nitrate, which is considered the least toxic compound for marine shrimp [3,12,13].

Although BFT is a system with numerous advantages, it requires some specific care, especially in relation to the TSS concentration [14]. In predominantly heterotrophic BFT cultures, the use of high carbon to nitrogen ratios (C:N) causes an increase in the production of bacterial biomass, increasing the system's demand for oxygen [14] and requiring removal of excess solids. Bacterial biomass, when not used in the system, creates an effluent with a high load of organic matter, rich in nitrogen and phosphorus, which, if not disposed of properly, can be an environmental issue [15,16]. Moreover, there are reports of negative effects on the health and performance of cultivated organisms when the system has high concentrations of solids, such as increased biological oxygen demand and occlusion of gills, which may compromise growth and survival rates [17,18]. Low TSS in BFT systems can be maintained by relying on a predominantly chemoautotrophic biofloc culture composed of nitrifying prokaryotes. These microorganisms have a significantly lower growth rate than heterotrophs and can maintain low TAN and low nitrite concentrations at lower biomass levels thanks to their efficient nitrification activities [19]. Another solution that can be used to maintain low TSS is integration with other species of interest in aquaculture that can consume and thereby control the concentration of solids, contributing to improved culture conditions [20,21].

In Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) systems, the use of organisms from different trophic levels in the same production system recreates the interactions that occur in the natural environment [22]. The goal of IMTA is to diversify production using species from different trophic levels, which may, in addition to fish, include bivalves, echinoderms, crustaceans, and algae, thereby maximizing the use of nutrients while limiting the use of water and the risk of ecological impact of production [23,24]. Nutrients not used by animals at the highest trophic level become a resource that allows the production of organisms at a lower trophic level. Thus, this culture strategy not only increases the economic value of production, since with the same amount of food it is possible to produce more species of economic value, it also improves water quality and reduces the concentration of nutrients in the effluent [25].

Both IMTA and BFT systems provide advantages, such as: optimizing the use of natural resources, reducing the use of land and water, allowing an increase in the productivity of the culture due to the use of high stocking densities, reducing environmental impacts, diversifying production, providing financial advantages for producers, and improving the social vision of aquaculture [4,26,27].

Considering the importance of microorganisms for the success of the culture and the lack of information about the microbial composition of IMTA systems, it is necessary to understand the effects of using predominantly chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic BFT systems on the planktonic community and on the nitrifying bacterial community structure. This must be done seeking to elucidate the function and activity of these communities and improve the management of IMTA systems. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of predominantly chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic biofloc systems on the establishment of AOB and NOB communities and the plankton composition in an integrated *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* multitrophic culture.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was carried out for 43 days at the “Estação Marinha de Aquicultura” of the “Universidade Federal do Rio Grande–FURG”, Brazil. This study was approved by the FURG Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee (process number: 23116.005895/2016-42).

2.1. Experimental Design and Conditions

The experiment was carried out in an aquaculture greenhouse. Each culture system consisted of two tanks: one larger tank with a volume of 20 m³ and one smaller tank with a volume of 4 m³. The larger tank was stocked with *P. vannamei* shrimp purchased from the AQUATEC hatchery, at a density of 400 shrimp m⁻². The smaller tank was stocked with tilapia juvenile (*O. niloticus*, GIFT strain) at a density of 45 fish m⁻³. Post-larvae shrimp were initially grown in a nursery and were stocked in the experimental units when they reached a mean weight of 1 g. Tilapia fingerlings (25 g) were acquired from a commercial larviculture facility (Piscicultura Acácias—Bonito, Camaquã, RS, Brazil) and maintained in a greenhouse in two tanks with a volume of 4 m³ with clear water and constant aeration. Prior to the beginning of the experiment, for 10 days, the fingerlings were acclimatized to salinity of 20 g L⁻¹. To achieve this, 10% of the freshwater was replaced with seawater every two days.

In each system, the tanks were interconnected for water recirculation through a submersible pump with a capacity of 2000 L h⁻¹ (SB 2700C Sarlo Better®, São Caetano do Su, SP, Brazil) installed in the shrimp tank that pumped the water to the tilapia tank and which, by gravity, returned to the shrimp tank (Figure 1). The experiment included two treatment groups, chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic, each with three independent replicates (six systems in total). Shrimp and tilapia were distributed among the systems in a randomized fashion.

Figure 1. Scheme of the multitrophic culture system of *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system.

2.2. Fertilization

For chemoautotrophic system development, 45 days prior to animal stocking, the three 20 m³ tanks were fertilized, once a day, with 1 mg L⁻¹ ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) and 1 mg L⁻¹ sodium nitrite (NaNO₂) to stimulate the growth of nitrifying bacteria [28].

In the heterotrophic system, the culture was started with clear water and, after stocking the animals, the total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) concentration was monitored daily until it reached 1 mg L^{-1} . From this moment on, sugar cane molasses was used as an organic carbon source in a carbon/nitrogen ratio of 15:1 [19,29]. This fertilization was carried out until the TAN concentration stabilized.

2.3. Feed Management

Throughout the experimental period, the animals were fed twice a day (8:00 a.m. and 4:00 p.m.) with the commercial feed Guabi (36% crude protein) for the tilapia and Guabi with 38% crude protein for the shrimp. The amount of feed offered to shrimp was determined according to Jory [30]. The tilapia was fed with 1% of the stocked biomass. This was done so that consumption of the bioflocs by the tilapia was stimulated.

2.4. Water Quality

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen (DO, mg L^{-1} ; oximeter YSI model Pro-20, YSI Incorporated, Yellow Springs, OH, USA), pH (pH meter Mettler Toledo, FEP20, METTLER TOLEDO, Oslo, Norway), total ammonia nitrogen (TAN, mg L^{-1}) [31], and nitrite nitrogen ($\text{NO}_2^{-}\text{-N}$, mg L^{-1}) [32] were monitored daily. Nitrate nitrogen ($\text{NO}_3^{-}\text{-N}$, mg L^{-1}) [33], orthophosphate (PO_4^{3-} , mg L^{-1}) [32], alkalinity (mg L^{-1}) [34], salinity (g L^{-1} ; Multiparameter Hanna, model HI98194, Hanna Instruments Ltd., Bedfordshire, UK), total suspended solids (TSS, mg L^{-1}) [35], and settleable solids (SS, mL L^{-1}) [36] were analyzed weekly.

2.5. Nitrifying Bacteria and Plankton Community Composition

Water samples from the shrimp and fish tanks were collected at the beginning and end of the trial, at the surface and at the bottom of the tank (with a Niskin bottle), to identify and quantify the different microbial groups in the system.

Quantification of two nitrifying bacterial groups (AOB and NOB) was carried out using fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH), following Cottrell and Kirchman [37]. First, the water samples were sonicated (Qsonica sonicators, model Q55) with three pulses of 30 s using a frequency of 10 kHz. Intervals of 1 min were included between each pulse. Subsequently, the samples were filtered through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ mean retention membrane and hybridized with oligonucleotide probes to quantify ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB: *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrosospira*) and nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB: *Nitrobacter* and *Nitrospira*). The probes were purchased from UNISCIENCE do Brazil (SP), and their references are presented in Table 1. All probes were labeled with fluorochrome Cy3. A negative control (NON) consisting of a probe without any specificity for bacteria was used to evaluate the hybridization efficiency. The total abundance of bacteria was determined by counting bacteria stained with DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) according to Cottrell and Kirchman [37] and Del'Duca et al. [38]. Bacterial abundance was obtained from direct counting using an epifluorescence microscope (AxioPlan Zeiss—Carl Zeiss do Brazil Ltda, Sao Paulo, SP, Brazil) at a final magnification of $1000\times$. The abundance of bacteria is expressed as organisms mL^{-1} .

Table 1. Oligonucleotide probes used to identify nitrifying bacteria in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* multitrophic culture with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system.

Probe	Specificity	Sequence 5'→3'	%F	Reference
NON	Negative control	TAGTGACGCCGTCGA	30	[39]
NEU	<i>Nitrosomonas</i>	CCCCTCTGCTGCACTCTA	40	[40]
NIT3	<i>Nitrobacter</i>	CCTGTGCTCCATGCTCCG	40	[41]
NSR447	<i>Nitrospira</i>	GGTTTCCCCTCCATCTT	30	[42]
Nsv443	<i>Nitrosospira</i>	CCGTGACCGTTTCGTTCCG	30	[43]

%F: percentage of formamide in the hybridization solution.

Phytoplankton and zooplankton species were identified and quantified with a sedimentation chamber on an inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse TS100, Microscope Central, Bustleton Pike, Feasterville, PA, USA) at a final magnification of 200× [44]. Abundance is expressed as organisms mL⁻¹.

2.6. Data Analysis

Water quality data were tested for normality, with the Shapiro–Wilk test, and homoscedasticity was tested with the Levene test. Differences between treatments were assessed with a repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA). When necessary, the data were transformed to fulfill parametric assumptions. For non-parametric data, the Friedman test was used to compare the treatments.

The abundance data of the main plankton groups, total abundance of bacteria, abundance of AOB and NOB, final weight, and survival of shrimp and tilapia were tested for normality with the Shapiro–Wilk test and for homoscedasticity with the Levene test. Differences between treatments were evaluated by *t* test. Survival percentage data were arcsine-transformed before analysis [45]. When necessary, data were transformed to fulfill parametric assumptions. For non-parametric data, the Wilcoxon test was used to compare groups.

Spearman correlation was calculated to verify the existence of correlations among the main water quality variables and the microbial community composition of the system.

A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was adopted for all tests. The graphs were drawn, and the Friedman test, *t* test, Wilcoxon test, and Spearman correlation were performed, using R software version 4.3.1 [46] with the following packages: car [47], stats [46], rstatix [48], corrplot [49], Hmisc [50], and ggplot2 [51]. Repeated measures ANOVA was performed using Past 4.03 2020 software [52].

3. Results

3.1. Water Quality

During the experimental period, the mean temperature varied between 28.87 and 29.00 °C between treatments. Dissolved oxygen was maintained above 5 mg L⁻¹, and the mean pH was close to 7.8 (Table 2).

Only two of the water quality parameters differed significantly between the treatments at an alpha level of 0.05. The TAN concentration was significantly higher in the heterotrophic treatment group, and the NO₃⁻-N concentration was significantly higher in the chemoautotrophic treatment group (Table 2).

Table 2. Water quality variables in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* multitrophic culture with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system.

Variable	Treatment	
	Chemoautotrophic	Heterotrophic
Temperature (°C)	28.87 ± 1.14	29.00 ± 1.33
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	5.77 ± 0.45	5.82 ± 0.49
pH	7.81 ± 0.12	7.83 ± 0.15
Salinity (g L ⁻¹)	21.58 ± 2.61	25.39 ± 1.41
TAN (mg L ⁻¹)	0.92 ± 1.36 ^b	2.21 ± 2.63 ^a
NO ₂ ⁻ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	4.57 ± 4.38	9.35 ± 7.62
NO ₃ ⁻ -N (mg L ⁻¹)	33.17 ± 12.53 ^a	9.70 ± 7.00 ^b
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	1.22 ± 1.05	0.93 ± 0.64
Alkalinity (mg L ⁻¹)	177.40 ± 24.24	160.20 ± 25.25
TSS (mg L ⁻¹)	254.50 ± 80.91	238.30 ± 76.20
SS (ml L ⁻¹)	6.54 ± 3.66	5.30 ± 3.82

Data are shown as the mean ± standard deviation. Superscript letters indicate statistically significant differences between the treatments (*p*-value < 0.05). DO: dissolved oxygen, TAN: total ammonia nitrogen, NO₂⁻-N: nitrite nitrogen, NO₃⁻-N: nitrate nitrogen, PO₄³⁻: orthophosphate, TSS: total suspended solids, and SS: settleable solids.

3.2. Nitrifying Bacterial Abundance

The abundance of AOB and NOB relative to the total abundance of bacteria was 0.43% at the beginning of the trial. At the end of the experimental period, the relative abundance of the two groups of bacteria in relation to the total abundance was less than 0.1% in both the chemoautotrophic and the heterotrophic treatment groups.

At the end of the experiment, the total abundance of bacteria was approximately two times higher in the heterotrophic treatment group (Figure 2a), while no significant differences were observed in AOB and NOB abundance between the treatment groups, neither at the beginning nor at the end of the trial (Figure 2b,c).

Figure 2. Total abundance of bacteria (organisms mL^{-1} , mean \pm standard deviation) (a), ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB, (b)), nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB, (c)), microalgae (d), flagellates (e), and ciliates (f) in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* multitrophic culture with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system. The different letters indicate whether there is a significant difference between the two conditions.

3.3. Phytoplankton and Zooplankton Composition

At the beginning of the trial, both treatment groups were dominated by ciliated protozoa, with nearly identical cell numbers observed in the two treatments (Figure 2f). In the final samples, both the chemoautotrophic and heterotrophic treatment groups were dominated by flagellates (Figure 2e).

At the end of the experimental period, the abundance of microalgae and ciliated protozoa was significantly higher in the chemoautotrophic treatment group compared to the heterotrophic group (Figure 2d,f).

3.4. Correlation Among Water Quality Variables and Microbial Composition

Total bacterial abundance was positively correlated with SS and nitrite concentrations and flagellate and microalgae abundances and negatively correlated with the total ammonia nitrogen concentration (Figure 3). The abundance of flagellates was positively correlated

with SS and orthophosphate concentrations and abundance of microalgae and negatively correlated with the total ammonia nitrogen and dissolved oxygen (Figure 3). The abundance of microalgae was positively correlated with TSS, SS, and orthophosphate concentrations and negatively correlated with the concentration of dissolved oxygen and total ammonia nitrogen (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Spearman correlation matrix among water quality variables and microbial community components in a *Penaeus vannamei* and *Oreochromis niloticus* multitrophic culture with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system. Numbers inside the boxes correspond to the correlation coefficient. * Significant correlations (p -value < 0.05). TAN: total ammonia nitrogen, DO: dissolved oxygen; TSS: total suspended solids; SS: settleable solids; TA: total abundance of bacteria.

3.5. Shrimp and Tilapia Growth

At the end of the experimental period, shrimp weights were significantly higher in the chemoautotrophic treatment group compared to the heterotrophic group, while there was no statistically significant difference in shrimp survival, which remained above 90%, between the treatment groups (Table 3). Neither the mean final weight of the tilapia nor the tilapia survival rate was significantly different between treatments (Table 3). The mean final weight of the tilapia varied between 171.60 and 180.80 g, with no significant differences between treatments. Survival varied between 76.19 and 83.81%, with no significant differences between treatments (Table 3).

Table 3. Growth of *Penaeus vannamei* shrimp and *Oreochromis niloticus* tilapia in a multitrophic culture with a predominantly chemoautotrophic or heterotrophic biofloc system.

Shrimp		
	Chemoautotrophic	Heterotrophic
Final weight (g)	6.63 ± 0.14 ^a	4.80 ± 0.12 ^b
Survival (%)	95.17 ± 2.69	92.54 ± 2.98
Tilapia		
	Chemoautotrophic	Heterotrophic
Final weight (g)	171.60 ± 17.81	180.80 ± 9.23
Survival (%)	76.19 ± 25.42	83.81 ± 8.93

Data are shown as the mean ± standard deviation. Superscript letters indicate statistically significant differences between the treatment groups (p -value < 0.05).

4. Discussion

Microorganisms are an essential part of all ecosystems [53]. Many microbial groups found in aquaculture systems can have a positive effect on the cultured species, through maintenance of good water quality and provisioning of microbial protein, serving as a supplementary food source [5,54]. In addition, the microbial community in biofloc systems can directly influence the composition of the intestinal flora and promote the health of aquatic organisms [55,56]. In a predominantly heterotrophic biofloc system, heterotrophic bacteria are important to the stability of the system, as they are involved in the digestion of excreta, uneaten food, and organic matter [19,57]. In predominantly chemoautotrophic biofloc systems, nitrifying bacteria have a direct effect on water quality, as they oxidize toxic nitrogenous compounds into forms that are less toxic to animals [58]. In shrimp farming systems, ammonia represents the major toxic nitrogen form that needs to be controlled; it results from protein catabolism of the feed offered [59]. This compound is the result of excretion from farmed animals and mineralization of organic debris such as uneaten feed and feces [60]. In predominantly heterotrophic systems, bacterial assimilation ensures removal of this toxic compound from the rearing water. The maintenance of water quality thus depends on appropriate balancing of microbial biomass (via carbon source amendment) and excreted ammonia concentration. In predominantly autotrophic systems, maintenance of water quality relies on the nitrification process. Therein, ammonia is first converted into nitrite, an intermediate product of the nitrification process, then to nitrate [61]. Bacteria that convert ammonia to nitrite (AOB) have a faster growth rate than those that convert nitrite to nitrate (NOB), especially in salt water [62]. Spikes in nitrogenous compounds can cause stress to animals, in addition to harming growth [63]. Thus, a proper balance between the abundance and activity of the two nitrifying groups is essential for successful removal of toxic nitrogen forms from chemoautotrophic systems. During the experiment reported here, the water quality in both treatments was maintained within acceptable ranges for the species, in terms of TAN and nitrite values.

As expected, a significantly higher total abundance of bacteria was observed in the heterotrophic treatment group. It has been reported that the production of microbial biomass in this system can be 40 times higher than that produced by predominantly chemoautotrophic systems [19]. In our study, a two-fold difference in bacterial abundance was found between the two systems, without significantly impacting the TSS. The heterotrophic biomass was sufficient to decrease ammonia concentrations to levels acceptable for the cultivated species. However, ammonia concentrations that were even lower were achieved in the chemoautotrophic treatment group. With half of the heterotrophic bacterial abundance (compared to the organic fertilization), the chemoautotrophic system was likely able to achieve more efficient ammonia removal due to the presence and high activity of nitrifying groups. AOB can have high efficiency, and, when they are completely established in the system, all the nitrogen produced in the form of ammonia can be immediately oxidized to nitrate [4]. The relative abundance of these bacterial groups (AOB and NOB) in relation to

the total abundance was very low (less than 0.1%) in both treatment groups. Moreover, the respective relative abundances of AOB and NOB were 50–50%, indicating a balanced distribution. The presence of such a well-established nitrifying community can be attributed to the inorganic fertilization carried out prior to the beginning of the experiment. However, the absence of significant differences in the abundance of AOB and NOB between treatment groups suggests that the abundance of the quantified groups alone cannot explain the better nitrification efficiency of the chemoautotrophic system. Our results demonstrate that both treatments were able to provide the necessary conditions for growth of the quantified groups of nitrifying bacteria; however, the achieved nitrification activity seemed to be different in the two systems. This may be explained by the presence of nitrifiers undetected by the method employed here (FISH) or a significant difference between the nitrification activity of the detected groups in the context of the two different systems.

In addition to promoting the establishment and growth of nitrifiers, the initial fertilizations with ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite carried out prior to shrimp stocking resulted in a planktonic community dominated by microalgae and ciliated protozoa in the chemoautotrophic treatment group at the end of the experimental period. The presence of excess inorganic nitrogen probably benefited the development of microalgae and, consequently, the growth of ciliates, which graze on the phytoplankton community. With regards to protozoa, one of the most relevant zooplankton groups playing a key role in organic matter recycling (along with bacteria), a general increase in both treatment groups was observed. This can be attributed to the consumption of organic matter and other microorganisms (e.g., bacteria) as food [7]. In fact, the volume of settleable solids and the total abundance of bacteria were positively correlated with the abundance of flagellated protozoa, indicating an interaction between these groups of microorganisms. Both groups are the basis of trophic transfer of energy to higher levels. They are abundant in many types of environments and are often found living freely in the water column or in colonizing sediments [54].

In intensive shrimp farming, the dominant microbial groups vary throughout the course of production as biotic and abiotic factors evolve and interact with each other. Typically, a photoautotrophic community (dominated by algae) develops first when light is available and becomes replaced by a heterotrophic community at later stages [64,65]. These patterns of dominance change the color of the water from greener to brownish shades [65]. Del Giorgio [66] pointed out that this change occurs when the amount of allochthonous carbon exceeds the amount of carbon supplied by phytoplankton to support microbial growth. The increase in the C:N ratio favors the dominance of the heterotrophic community in the system and the assimilation of nitrogenous compounds to produce microbial protein [29,67]. These changes in microbial dominance often imply significant changes in water quality conditions, such as an increase in the concentration of total suspended solids and nutrients such as carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus [68]. In this study we observed a positive correlation between SST and SS and the abundance of microalgae. A high load of microalgae was produced in both treatment groups, especially in the chemoautotrophic group, and this can be explained by the incidence of light in the system. According to Coyle et al. [69], light can affect both cultured animals and the microbiota in the medium. Another factor that may have also driven the growth of microalgae in the system was the presence of orthophosphate (positive correlation between orthophosphate and microalgae abundance). In the presence of light and nutrients, microalgae find the perfect conditions for growth, serving as the base of the food chain for the development of zooplankton and representing an important source of supplementary food for shrimp [70].

Regardless of the carbon source used in the fertilization process, it was possible to observe the development of the microbial loop, resulting in an environment rich in various planktonic microorganisms, which is an essential feature of biofloc systems [71,72]. Better control of nitrogenous compounds and the load of microorganisms grown in the chemoautotrophic treatment appeared to influence shrimp growth positively.

5. Conclusions

The use of either a predominantly chemoautotrophic or a predominantly heterotrophic biofloc system did not significantly alter the total abundance of selected AOB and NOB in a *P. vannamei* and *O. niloticus* multitrophic culture. Despite the better control of nitrogen compounds in the chemoautotrophic treatment group and the differing microbial assemblages found in the two systems, the two fertilization strategies proved to be equally efficient for maintaining good water quality and sufficient growth of both shrimp and tilapia. Furthermore, shrimp growth was higher in the chemoautotrophic treatment group, which may have been influenced by the higher load of microalgae produced in that treatment group. Overall, our study demonstrated that chemoautotrophic fertilization is a promising approach in integrated biofloc cultivation of shrimp and fish.

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References

1. Panigrahi, R.; Srivastava, P.R.; Sharma, D. Online Learning: Adoption, Continuance, and Learning Outcome—A Review of Literature. *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* **2018**, *43*, 1–14. [[CrossRef](#)]
2. Costa, B.B.; Streit Júnior, D.P. Cultivo De Camarões Em Sistema De Bioflocos No Brasil: Uma Alternativa Sustentável Às Intensificações Na Aquicultura. *Arq. Ciências Mar* **2019**, *51*, 116. [[CrossRef](#)]
3. Avnimelech, Y.; Kochba, M. Evaluation of nitrogen uptake and excretion by tilapia in bio floc tanks, using ¹⁵N tracing. *Aquaculture* **2009**, *287*, 163–168. [[CrossRef](#)]
4. Avnimelech, Y. *Biofloc Technology—A Practical Guide Book*, 2nd ed.; The World Aquaculture Society: Baton Rouge, LA, USA, 2012; p. 272.
5. De Schryver, P.; Crab, R.; Defoirdt, T.; Boon, N.; Verstraete, W. The basics of bioflocs technology: The added value for aquaculture. *Aquaculture* **2008**, *277*, 125–137. [[CrossRef](#)]
6. Wasielesky, W.; Atwood, H.; Stokes, A.; Browdy, C.L. Effect of natural production in a zero exchange suspended microbial floc based super-intensive culture system for white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquaculture* **2006**, *258*, 396–403. [[CrossRef](#)]
7. Manan, H.; Moh, J.H.Z.; Kasan, N.A.; Suratman, S.; Ikhwanuddin, M. Identification of biofloc microscopic composition as the natural bioremediation in zero water exchange of Pacific white shrimp, *Penaeus vannamei*, culture in closed hatchery system. *Appl. Water Sci.* **2017**, *7*, 2437–2446. [[CrossRef](#)]

8. Krummenauer, D.; Peixoto, S.; Cavalli, R.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W. Superintensive culture of White shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, in a biofloc technology system in Southern Brazil at different stocking densities. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* **2011**, *42*, 726–733. [CrossRef]
9. Yu, Y.-B.; Lee, J.-H.; Choi, J.-H.; Choi, Y.J.; Jo, A.-H.; Choi, C.Y.; Kang, J.-C.; Kim, J.-H. The application and future of biofloc technology (BFT) in aquaculture industry: A review. *J. Environ. Manag.* **2023**, *342*, 118237. [CrossRef]
10. Samocha, T.M.; Prangnell, D.I.; Hanson, T.R.; Treece, G.D.; Morris, T.C.; Castro, L.F.; Staresinic, N. *Design and Operation of Super-Intensive Biofloc—Dominated Systems for Indoor Production of the Pacific White Shrimp, Litopenaeus vannamei—The Texas A&M AgriLife Research Experience*; The World Aquaculture Society: Baton Rouge, LA, USA, 2017.
11. Serra, F.P.; Gaona, C.A.P.; Furtado, P.S.; Poersch, L.H.; Wasielesky, W., Jr. Use of different carbon sources for the biofloc system adopted during the nursery and grow-out culture of *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *Aquacult. Int.* **2015**, *23*, 1325–1339. [CrossRef]
12. Ootoshi, C.A.; Moss, N.R. Establishing Nitrifying Bacteria in Super-Intensive Biofloc Shrimp Production. Global Aquaculture Advocate, May–June 2011. Available online: <https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/establishing-nitrifying-bacteria-in-super-intensive-biofloc-shrimp-production/> (accessed on 10 June 2024).
13. Avnimelech, Y. *Biofloc Technology—A Practical Guide Book*, 3rd ed.; The World Aquaculture Society: Baton Rouge, LA, USA, 2015; p. 258.
14. Fleckenstein, L.J.; Kring, N.A.; Tierney, T.W.; Fisk, J.C.; Lawson, B.C.; Ray, A.J. The effects of artificial substrate and stoking density on Pacific White shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) performance and water quality dynamics in high tunnel-based biofloc systems. *Aquac. Eng.* **2020**, *90*, 102093. [CrossRef]
15. Ray, A.J.; Seaborn, G.; Leffler, J.W.; Wilder, S.B.; Lawson, A.; Browdy, C.L. Characterization of microbial communities in minimal-exchange, intensive aquaculture systems and the effects of suspended solids management. *Aquaculture* **2010**, *310*, 130–138. [CrossRef]
16. Silva, K.R.; Wasielesky, W.; Abreu, P.C. Nitrogen and Phosphorus Dynamics in the Biofloc Production of the Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* **2013**, *44*, 30–41. [CrossRef]
17. Gaona, C.A.P.; Poersch, L.H.; Krummenauer, D.; Foes, G.K.; Wasielesky, W. The Effect of Solids Removal on Water Quality, Growth and Survival of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a Biofloc Technology Culture System. *Int. J. Recirc. Aquac.* **2011**, *12*, 54–73. [CrossRef]
18. Schweitzer, R.; Arantes, R.; Costodio, P.F.S.; Santo, C.M.D.; Arana, L.V.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Andreatta, E.R. Effect of different biofloc levels on microbial activity, water quality and performance of *Litopenaeus vannamei* in a tank system operated with no water exchange. *Aquac. Eng.* **2013**, *56*, 59–70. [CrossRef]
19. Ebeling, J.M.; Timmons, M.B.; Bisogni, J.J. Engineering analysis of the stoichiometry of photoautotrophic, autotrophic, and heterotrophic removal of ammonia-nitrogen in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* **2006**, *257*, 346–358. [CrossRef]
20. Chopin, T.; Cooper, J.; Reid, G.; Cross, S.; Moore, S. Open water integrated multi-trophic aquaculture: Environmental biomitigation and economic diversification of fed aquaculture by extractive aquaculture. *Rev. Aquac.* **2012**, *4*, 209–220. [CrossRef]
21. Troell, M.; Joyce, A.; Chopin, T.; Neori, A.; Buschmann, A.H.; Fang, J.G. Ecological engineering in aquaculture—Potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine offshore systems. *Aquaculture* **2009**, *297*, 1–9. [CrossRef]
22. Bakke, I.; Åm, A.L.; Kolarevic, J.; Ytrestøyl, T.; Vadstein, O.; Attramadal, K.J.K.; Terjesen, B.F. Microbial community dynamics in semi-commercial RAS for production of Atlantic salmon post-smolts at different salinities. *Aquac. Eng.* **2017**, *78*, 42–49. [CrossRef]
23. Barrington, K.; Chopin, T.; Robinson, S. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in marine temperate waters. In *Integrated Mariculture: A Global Review*; FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper; FAO: Rome, Italy, 2009; Volume 529, pp. 7–46.
24. Poli, M.A.; Legarda, E.C.; De Lorenzo, M.A.; Pinheiro, I.; Martins, M.A.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Integrated multitrophic aquaculture applied to shrimp rearing in a biofloc system. *Aquaculture* **2019**, *511*, 734274. [CrossRef]
25. Neori, A.; Chopin, T.; Troell, M.; Buschmann, A.H.; Kraemer, G.P.; Halling, C.; Shpigel, M.; Yarish, C. Integrated aquaculture: Rationale, evolution and state of the art emphasizing seaweed biofiltration in modern mariculture. *Aquaculture* **2004**, *231*, 361–391. [CrossRef]
26. Liu, L.; Hu, Z.; Dai, X.; Avnimelech, Y. Effects of addition of maize starch on the yield, water quality and formation of bioflocs in an integrated shrimp culture system. *Aquaculture* **2014**, *418*, 79–86. [CrossRef]
27. Poli, M.A.; Legarda, E.C.; De Lorenzo, M.A.; Martins, M.A.; Vieira, F.N. Pacific white shrimp and Nile tilapia integrated in a biofloc system under different fish-stocking densities. *Aquaculture* **2018**, *498*, 83–89. [CrossRef]
28. Ferreira, G.S.; Santos, D.; Schmachtl, F.; Machado, C.; Fernandes, V.; Bögner, M.; Schleder, D.D.; Seiffert, W.Q.; Vieira, F.N. Heterotrophic, chemoautotrophic and mature approaches in biofloc system for Pacific white shrimp. *Aquaculture* **2021**, *533*, 736099. [CrossRef]
29. Avnimelech, Y. Carbon: Nitrogen ratio as a control element in aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* **1999**, *176*, 227–235. [CrossRef]
30. Jory, D.E. Feed management practices for a healthy pond environment. In *The New Wave, Proceedings of the Special Session on Sustainable Shrimp Culture*; Browdy, C.L., Jory, D.E., Eds.; The World Aquaculture Society: Baton Rouge, LA, USA, 2001; Volume 375, pp. 118–143.
31. UNESCO. *Chemical Methods for Use in Marine Environmental Monitoring*; Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission—Manuals and Guides; UNESCO: Paris, France, 1983; p. 12.
32. Aminot, A.; Chaussepied, M. *Manuel des Analyses Chimiques en Milieu Marin*; CNEXO: Paris, France, 1983.
33. García-Robledo, E.; Corzo, A.; Papaspyrou, S. A fast and direct spectrophotometric method for the sequential determination of nitrate and nitrite at low concentrations in small volumes. *Mar. Chem.* **2014**, *162*, 30–36. [CrossRef]

34. APHA. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 22nd ed.; American Public Health Association: Washington, DC, USA, 2012.
35. Strickland, J.D.H.; Parsons, T.R. *A Practical Handbook of Seawater Analysis*, 2nd ed.; Fisheries Research Board of Canada: Ottawa, ON, Canada, 1972.
36. Eaton, D.E.; Clesceri, L.S.; Greenberg, A.E. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*, 19th ed.; American Public Health Association: Washington, DC, USA, 1995.
37. Cottrell, M.T.; Kirchman, D.L. Contribution of major bacterial groups to bacterial biomass production (*thymidine* and *leucine* incorporation) in the Delaware estuary. *Limnol. Oceanogr.* **2003**, *48*, 168–178. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Del'Duca, A.; Cesar, D.E.; Diniz, C.G.; Abreu, P.C. Evaluation of the presence and efficiency of potential probiotic bacteria in the gut of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) using the fluorescent in situ hybridization technique. *Aquaculture* **2013**, *388–391*, 115–121. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Yokokawa, T.; Nagata, T. Growth and grazing mortality rates of phylogenetic groups of bacterioplankton in coastal marine environments. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2005**, *71*, 6799–6807. [[CrossRef](#)]
40. Wagner, M.; Rath, G.; Amann, R.; Koops, H.P.; Schleifer, K.H. In situ Identification of Ammonia-oxidizing Bacteria. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* **1995**, *18*, 251–264. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Wagner, M.; Rath, G.; Koops, H.P.; Flood, J.; Amann, R. In situ analysis of nitrifying bacteria in sewage treatment plants. *Water Sci. Technol.* **1996**, *34*, 237–244. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Schramm, A.; De Beer, D.; Wagner, M.; Amann, R. Identification and activities in situ of *Nitrosospira* and *Nitrospira* spp. as dominant populations in a nitrifying fluidized bed reactor. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **1998**, *64*, 3480–3485. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
43. Mobarry, B.K.; Wagner, M.; Urbain, V.; Rittmann, B.E.; Stahl, D.A. Phylogenetic probes for analyzing abundance and spatial organization of nitrifying bacteria. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **1996**, *62*, 2156–2162. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Utermöhl, H. Zur Vervollkommnung der quantitativen Phytoplankton-Methodik. *Mitt. Int. Ver. Theor. Angew. Limnol.* **1958**, *9*, 1–38. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Zar, J.H. *Biostatistical Analysis*, 5th ed.; Pearson Prentice Hall: New Jersey, NJ, USA, 2010; p. 248.
46. R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*; R Foundation for Statistical Computing: Vienna, Austria, 2023. Available online: <https://www.R-project.org/> (accessed on 10 June 2024).
47. Fox, J.; Weisberg, S. *An R Companion to Applied Regression*, 3rd ed.; Sage: Thousand Oaks, CA, USA, 2019.
48. Kassambara, A. Rstatix: Pipe-Friendly Framework for Basic Statistical Tests. R Package Version 0.7.2. 2023. Available online: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rstatix> (accessed on 10 June 2024).
49. Wei, T.; Simko, V. R Package 'Corrplot': Visualization of a Correlation Matrix (Version 0.92). 2021. Available online: <https://github.com/taiyun/corrplot> (accessed on 10 June 2024).
50. Harrell, F., Jr. Hmisc: Harrell Miscellaneous. R Package Version 5.0-1. 2023. Available online: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=Hmisc> (accessed on 10 June 2024).
51. Wickham, H. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*; Springer-Verlag: New York, NY, USA, 2016.
52. Hammer, Ø.; Harper, D.A.T.; Ryan, P.D. PAST: Paleontological Statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Paleontol. Electronica* **2001**, *4*, 9.
53. Lopez, L.A.; Zaballo, A. Diversidad y actividad procariota en ecosistemas marinos. *Rev. Ecosistemas* **2005**, *14*, 30–40.
54. Emerenciano, M.; Martínez-Córdova, L.R.; Martínez-Porchas, M.; Miranda Baeza, A. *Biofloc Technology (BFT): A Tool for Water Quality Management in Aquaculture*; InTech: London, UK, 2017; pp. 91–109.
55. Chaiyapechara, S.; Rungrassamee, W.; Suriyachay, I.; Kuncharin, Y.; Klanchui, A.; Karoonuthaisiri, N.; Jiravanichpaisal, P. Bacterial Community Associated with the Intestinal Tract of *P. monodon* in Commercial Farms. *Microb. Ecol.* **2012**, *63*, 938–953. [[CrossRef](#)]
56. Cardona, E.; Gueguen, Y.; Magr'e, K.; Lorgeoux, B.; Piquemal, D.; Pierrat, F. Bacterial community characterization of water and intestine of the shrimp *Litopenaeus stylirostris* in a biofloc system. *BMC Microbiol.* **2016**, *16*, 1–9. [[CrossRef](#)]
57. Monroy-Dosta, M.D.C.; Lara-Andrade, D.; Castro-Mejía, J.; Castro-Mejía, G.; Emerenciano, M.G. Microbiology community composition and abundance associated to biofloc in tilapia aquaculture. *Rev. Biol. Mar. Oceanogr.* **2013**, *48*, 511–520. [[CrossRef](#)]
58. Musyoka, S. Concept of microbial bioremediation in aquaculture wastes: Review. *Int. J. Adv. Sci. Tech. Res.* **2016**, *5*, 1–10.
59. Timmons, M.B.; Ebeling, J.M.; Wheaton, F.W.; Summerfelt, S.T.; Vinci, B.J. *Recirculating Aquaculture Systems*, 2nd ed.; Cayuga Aqua Ventures: New York, NY, USA, 2002; p. 769.
60. Lin, Y.C.; Chen, J.C. Acute toxicity of ammonia on *Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone juveniles at different salinity levels. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecology.* **2001**, *259*, 109–119. [[CrossRef](#)]
61. Thurston, R.V.; Russo, R.C.; Smith, C.E. Acute toxicity of ammonia and nitrite to cutthroat trout fry. *Trans. Am. Fish. Soc.* **1978**, *107*, 361–368. [[CrossRef](#)]
62. Madigan, M.T.; Martinko, J.M.; Bender, K.S.; Buckley, D.H.; Stahl, D.A. *Microbiologia de Brock*, 14th ed.; Artmed: Porto Alegre, Brazil, 2016.
63. Cohen, J.M.; Samocha, T.M.; Fox, J.M.; Gandy, R.L.; Lawrence, A.L. Characterization of water quality factors during intensive raceway production of juvenile *Litopenaeus vannamei* using limited discharge and biosecure management tools. *Aquac. Eng.* **2005**, *32*, 425–442. [[CrossRef](#)]

64. Kirk, K.R. Modeling Microbial and Nutrient Dynamics in Zero-Discharge Aquaculture Systems. Ph.D. Thesis, Clemson University, Clemson, SC, USA, 2010. Available online: https://tigerprints.clemson.edu/all_dissertations/648 (accessed on 10 June 2024).
65. Hargreaves, J.A. Biofloc Production Systems for Aquaculture Southern regional aquaculture center. *SRAC Publ.* **2013**, *4503*, 1–12.
66. Del Giorgio, P.A.; Cole, J.J.; Cimbleris, A. Respiration rates in bacteria exceed phytoplankton production in unproductive aquatic systems. *Nature* **1997**, *385*, 148–151. [[CrossRef](#)]
67. Burford, M.A.; Lorenzen, K. Modeling nitrogen dynamics in intensive shrimp ponds: The role of sediments remineralization. *Aquaculture* **2004**, *229*, 129–145. [[CrossRef](#)]
68. Pimentel, O.A.L.F.; Amado, A.M.; They, N.H. Biofloc colors as an assessment tool for water quality in shrimp farming with BFT systems. *Aquac. Eng.* **2023**, *101*, 102321. [[CrossRef](#)]
69. Coyle, S.D.; Bright, L.A.; Wood, D.R.; Neal, R.S.; Tidwell, J.H. Performance of Pacific White Shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, Reared in Zero-Exchange Tank Systems Exposed to Different Light Sources and Intensities. *J. World Aquac. Soc.* **2011**, *42*, 687–695. [[CrossRef](#)]
70. Ju, Z.Y.; Forster, I.; Conquest, L.; Dominy, W.; Kuo, W.C.; Horgen, F.D. Determination of microbial community structures of shrimp floc cultures by biomarkers and analysis of floc amino acid profiles. *Aquac. Res.* **2008**, *39*, 118–133. [[CrossRef](#)]
71. Ahmad, I.; Leya, T.; Saharan, N.; Majeedkutti, B.R.A.; Rathore, G.; Gora, H.; Bhat, I.A.; Verma, A.K. Carbon sources affect water quality and haemato-biochemical responses of *Labeo rohita* in zero-water ractica biofloc system. *Aquac. Res.* **2019**, *50*, 2879–2887. [[CrossRef](#)]
72. Khanjani, M.H.; Alizadeh, M.; Sharifinia, M. Effects of different carbon sources on water quality, biofloc quality, and growth performance of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fingerlings in a heterotrophic culture system. *Aquac. Int.* **2021**, *29*, 307–321. [[CrossRef](#)]

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